

**PLOT OF FICTION: PLOT STRUCTURE IN WORKS CHARACTERIZING THE
IMAGE OF TEMURIAN PRINCESSES IN UZBEK DRAMA**

Jumanova Orzigul Sa'dulla qizi

Researcher, Department of Foreign Languages,

Karshi State Technical University

ANNOTATION: This article analyzes the plot construction and its specific features in works of art, especially in dramaturgy, based on the definitions of literary scholars. In particular, the image of the Timurid princesses in Uzbek dramaturgy and their role in the plot are analyzed. The article uses a scientific-analytical approach and summarizes the theoretical views of scholars such as Abdulla Qahhor, V. Tomashevsky, M. Quranov and B. Karim on the plot. Also, specific analytical examples are given based on one of the historical dramas - the drama "Ulug'bek". According to the results of the analysis, the development of the plot through internal and external conflicts in the images of the Timurid princesses, in particular Firyuza, Gavharshod and Nigorkhanim, was shown. The image of Firyuza was highly appreciated as a symbol of loyalty, conscience and moral purity. The conflict of social stratification and moral values in palace life was highlighted as the main dramatic force. The article emphasizes that the plot of the historical drama is based on the harmony of reality and artistic texture. The image of Firyuza is interpreted as an exemplary image for modern man. The main idea of the work is the call for human values, inner purity, and social justice.

Keywords: plot, Mirzo Ulugbek's drama, Timurid princesses, Gavharshodbeg, drama, plot construction, historical and artistic image

ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqolada badiiy asarlarda, xususan dramaturgiyada syujet qurilishi va uning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari adabiyotshunoslar ta'riflari asosida sharhlanadi. Ayniqsa, o'zbek dramaturgiyasida Temuriy malikalar obrazining tasviri va ularning syujetdagi roli tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada ilmiy-tahliliy yondashuv qo'llanilib, Abdulla Qahhor, V. Tomashevskiy, M. Quranov va B. Karim kabi olimlarning syujet haqidagi nazariy qarashlari umumlashtiriladi. Shuningdek, tarixiy dramalardan biri — "Ulug'bek" dramasi asosida konkret tahliliy misollar keltiriladi. Tahlil natijalariga ko'ra, temuriy malikalar obrazlari, xususan Firyuza, Gavharshod va Nigorkhonim timsollarida syujet ichki va tashqi konfliktlar orqali rivojlanishi ko'rsatildi. Firyuza obrazi sadoqat, vijdon va axloqiy poklik ramzi sifatida yuksak baholandi. Saroy hayotidagi ijtimoiy tabaqalashtirish va axloqiy qadriyatlar ziddiyati asosiy

dramatik kuch sifatida yoritildi. Maqolada tarixiy drama syujetining voqelik va badiiy to'qima uyg'unligiga asoslanganligi ta'kidlanadi. Firyuza obrazi zamonaviy inson uchun ham ibratli qiyofa sifatida talqin qilinadi. Asarda insoniy qadriyatlar, ichki poklik va ijtimoiy adolatga da'vat asosiy g'oya sifatida ilgari suriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: syujet, Mirzo Ulug'bek dramasi, temuriy malikalar, gavharshodbegim, drama, syujet qurilishi, tarixiy va badiiy obraz

АННОТАЦИЯ: В данной статье анализируется построение сюжета и его специфические особенности в художественных произведениях, особенно в драматургии, на основе определений литературоведов. В частности, анализируется образ тимуридских принцесс в узбекской драматургии и их роль в сюжете. В статье используется научно-аналитический подход и обобщаются теоретические взгляды таких ученых, как Абдулла Каххор, В. Томашевский, М. Куранов и Б. Карим на сюжет. Также приводятся конкретные аналитические примеры на основе одной из исторических драм - драмы «Улугбек». По результатам анализа показано развитие сюжета через внутренние и внешние конфликты в образах тимуридских принцесс, в частности Фирюзы, Гавхаршод и Нигорханим. Образ Фирюзы высоко ценился как символ верности, совести и нравственной чистоты. В качестве основной драматической силы был выделен конфликт социальной стратификации и моральных ценностей в дворцовой жизни. В статье подчеркивается, что сюжет исторической драмы основан на гармонии реальности и художественной фактуры. Образ Фирюзы трактуется как образцовый образ для современного человека. Основная идея произведения — призыв к общечеловеческим ценностям, внутренней чистоте, социальной справедливости.

Ключевые слова: сюжет, драма Мирзо Улугбека, тимуридские принцессы, Гавхаршодбег, драма, построение сюжета, историко-художественный образ

INTRODUCTION. Before considering the plot of works that highlight the image of the Timurid maikas, we found it advisable to explain what plot construction is in works of art, using the definitions given by literary scholars and our own personal conclusions. The people's writer of Uzbekistan, Abdulla Qahhor, in his work "Fundamentals of Literary Theory", defines plot as follows: "The plot is a sequential expression of the development of events and phenomena, the movement of images, the conflicts and struggles between them" [1;142]. Russian formalist V. Tomashevsky says, "The plot is an artistically organized form of reality. It is not real life, but the writer's selected and processed material." [2;78] "The existence of the plot serves to artistically express reality through dramatic contradictions. This aspect is especially important

in historical works,” emphasizes M. Qurbanov in his work “Artistic Thought and Imagery” [3;212]. If we summarize the definitions given by writers and literary critics to the plot with our own thoughts, the plot is the compositional and logical arrangement of events in a work of art, through which the author reveals the idea. The plot is the "skeleton" of the work, which is the development of events in the work in time and causal order, that is, the system of events narrated within the work. It expresses the actions of the characters, the conflict, the climax and the resolution in an orderly manner. Its main parts are as follows:

Introduction (exposition)

Conflict (conflict)

Development

Climax (culmination)

Resolution (resolution)

METHODS (METHODS) A general understanding of the plot was formed on the basis of scientific literature, theoretical views of literary critics and analytical methods. A practical analysis was carried out on the basis of examples of historical dramas, in particular, fragments of scenes from the drama "Ulug'bek". The main conflicts that determine the development of the plot in the work, the decisions of the characters and the relationships between them were analyzed. An attempt was made to reveal the role of the actions, views and moral principles of the characters in the formation of the plot.

Dramaturgy is a work written for the stage, in which the plot construction develops through conflicts, which is different from other works of art. It is the conflict that sets the plot in motion and its main stages consist of the following:

Exposition - the beginning of the work, the characters, the environment are introduced.

Node - the main conflict arises.

Climax - the conflict reaches its highest point.

Resolution - events move towards a resolution.

Resolution - the conflict is resolved, the work is completed.

The peculiarity of the plot in drama is that it is shown in action, that is, it is revealed through actions on the stage, and dialogues serve as the main tool.

Each scene should move events forward without unnecessary details. In the work “Fundamentals of Modern Dramaturgy”, B. Karim explains dramaturgy and the plot in it as follows: “The art of dramaturgy is the art of revealing characters through actions. And action is the heart of the plot.” [4;45]

RESULTS. According to the results of the analysis, in the drama "Ulug'bek" the images of Firyuza, Gavharshod and Nigorkhanim were shown as the main driving forces of the plot development. Through the image of Firyuza, the ideas of loyalty, conscience and purity were exalted. Characters such as Gavharshod and Nigorkhanim were depicted as images protecting social stratification and order in the palace. Internal conflicts and contradictions between the women of the palace create the main dramatic force in the drama. Despite her simple origin, Firyuza maintains her moral superiority, and through this, human values are put in the main place in the work.

In a historical drama, the plot is based on real events. Historical figures are embodied as the main characters. Events are clearly defined in terms of time and space. The harmony of historical truth and artistic texture is of great importance. Gavharshodbegim - a major political and cultural figure in the history of the Timurid era. The drama "Ulugbek" is a vivid example of historical dramas in Uzbek literature, in which the life and activities of the great scholar and statesman of the 15th century Mirzo Ulugbek are artistically interpreted. This excerpt clearly shows how the work reflects the complex socio-political relations, human values, and moral principles within the palace. The excerpt, which presents the main plot and conflict, mainly illuminates the main internal conflict in the drama through dialogues between Firyuza, Gavharshod, Nigorkhanim, and other court ladies. There is discontent within the palace about Firyuza and her closeness to Ulugbek. The women see her as a commoner who does not fit into the court's rules, which shows the stratification within the court and the inferiority complex that the upper class has towards those below them.

Firyuza, on the other hand, does not act against them, but remains true to her truth. Her inner loyalty, purity of conscience, and boundless respect for her teacher (Ulugbek) are clearly felt in each of her answers:

"My duty, my duty of conscience, mother! Because he is my teacher... and my legal husband!" These words show how pure and courageous Firyuza's character is.

Character analysis Firyuza is a symbol of loyalty and conscience. She does not give in to the luxury and pomp of the palace, but rather puts human values above all. She puts love and loyalty above personal interests. Despite her simple origin, Firyuza does not surrender her honor and pride to anyone. Despite the intrigues in the palace, she defends her loyalty and purity. Gavharshod is an image that protects power and authority. He demands to preserve the palace traditions and live in accordance with them. For Gavharshod, order and prestige are the most important values. In his opinion, an ordinary woman poses a threat to the prestige of the palace.

Nigorkhanim is a character who expresses the general mood and thoughts in the palace. She also accuses women like Firyuza of not complying with the palace rules and expresses her opinion against them. Abdullatif is seen here as a character who represents a weighty and soft approach. He tries to soften the argument, comparing it to traditional life situations and advocates not to escalate the conflict.

DISCUSSION. The article emphasizes that in historical dramas, the plot is built on the basis of the harmony of reality and artistic texture. In the drama "Ulugbek", the values of loyalty and conscience are shown as universal ideas that do not lose their significance even in historical conditions. The image of Firyuza is interpreted as a heroine who can be an example in modern life. The social stratification and conflict of moral values in the palace enhanced the internal dynamism of the plot. The article highlights the aesthetic and educational significance of the images of Timurid princesses in Uzbek dramaturgy through the combination of artistic thinking and historical consciousness. The main ideas in the drama are loyalty and conscience - Firyuza values a life based on loyalty and conscience. It highlights the need not to forget about conscience and duty even in difficult circumstances.

Palace order and stratification - The strict hierarchy and stratification system in palace life is criticized. Firyuza, as an ordinary person, resists views from above. Conflict between women - It shows how competition and jealousy arise between women within the palace and how this affects the overall mood. Moral strength and culture - Firyuza draws her strength from her commitment to moral principles and culture. This fundamentally distinguishes her from other court ladies. External and internal struggle The conflict in the drama is manifested not only in external conflicts, but also in internal struggles. Firyuza internally fights against oppression, doubts and discrimination against herself. This internal struggle gives her spiritual strength and further strengthens her personality. In conclusion, this excerpt reveals the spiritual and philosophical layers of the drama "Ulugbek". Values such as loyalty, conscience, purity and moral superiority are sung in the image of Firyuza. Characters such as Gavharshod and Nigorkhanim are expressions of the political and social order in court life. The work encourages the reader to think deeply, appreciate human values and maintain inner purity. Firyuza is an image that can serve as an example for every person, both in historical conditions and in modern life.

REFERENCES:

1. Qahhor A. "Fundamentals of Literary Theory", Tashkent, 1979, p. 142

2. Tomashevsky V. “Theory of Literature”, Moscow, 1925, p. 78
3. Kuronov M. “Artistic Thought and Imagery”, Tashkent, 2004, p. 212
4. Babur Karim, “Fundamentals of Modern Dramaturgy”, Tashkent, 2011, p. 45
5. Maqsud Shaikhzoda, “Mirzo Ulug’bek”, Tashkent, 2019

